

Research Article

Assessment of Heavy Metals in Total Atmospheric Deposit (TAD) obtained in Owode, Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The TAD, heavy metals, and source identification of samples obtained in Owode, Ondo State, Nigeria were determined in this study. TAD was collected once every month. Heavy metals (Fe, Zn, Ni, Pb, Cr, and Cu) were determined using XRF instrumentation. The results obtained showed that the TAD was within the range of 100.40 and 285.30 g m⁻³ day⁻¹ with a mean value of 177.73 at 95% confidence intervals. From the study, it was observed that the range of elemental composition was as follows: Fe > Zn > Cu > Cr > Pb > Ni. High correlations were obtained in the followings, Ni:Fe ($r^2=0.66$), Cu:Fe ($r^2=0.87$), Pb:Fe ($r^2=0.72$), Pb:Cr ($r^2=0.84$), Pb:Cu ($r^2=0.78$), Zn:Fe ($r^2=0.61$), while low correlation was between Fe:TAD ($r^2=0.48$). The potential source identification was done by using Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The values of the heavy metals (Pb and Cr) in PC2 were greater than the corresponding values, which showed that human activities (traffic/vehicular movements) were a major influence. The sources of Cu were attributed to agricultural activities, including biomass burning.

Keywords: Total Atmospheric Deposits, heavy metals, PCA, XRF, source identification

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Introduction

Anthropogenic and non-anthropogenic activities world-wide are the causes of atmospheric pollution. The particles generated during these activities are transported

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over a long distance by the prevailing wind at different speeds and directions. According to Onwudiegwu *et al.* (2015), wet and dry fallout also occur locally, and atmospheric fluxes onto impervious urban surfaces may significantly contribute to the contamination of urban runoff and play an important role in the urban cycle of metals, and further downstream on the contamination of receiving ecosystems. The particles released into the atmosphere when aggregated or washed out by rain are called atmospheric deposition, respectively, dry and wet (Azimi *et al.*, 2003). While dry deposition of particles occurs by direct impact and gravitational settling on land or water surfaces, then wet deposition, aerosols, and gases are dissolved or suspended in water droplets or ice crystals. Long-range transport processes, significant dry and wet depositions also occur locally, and atmospheric sources in urban areas may play an important role in the metal contamination of dry and wet depositions (Person *et al.*, 1993).

The total amount of heavy metals in the atmosphere is usually used as the main or only evaluation criteria for assessing the pollution conditions (Li *et al.*, 2013). Generally, it is recognized that the chemical speciation of a heavy metal determines its bioavailability and the potential risks it poses to the environment and to human health (Pérez *et al.*, 2013). The heavy metal chemical speciation in a solid environmental sample can generally be determined by sequentially extracting the different species as the adsorbed-exchangeable carbonate phase, the reducible phase, the oxidizable phase, and the residual fraction (Li *et al.*, 2013). The first three of those species' types, especially the adsorbed-exchangeable carbonate phase, are considered to be more mobile in the environment and more hazardous to organisms than is the resistant fraction (Pérez *et al.*, 2013).

According to Abulude *et al.* (2018), the quality of living and non-living things depends on air and water quality. In Owode, Ondo State, Nigeria a study conducted by Abulude *et al.* (2019) showed that the air quality may be a little bit problematic. To confirm this, the heavy metals of the TAD in the vicinity were determined using standard methods and XRF for instrumentation.

Assessing the extent of the contributions from various sources to the TAD has always been a big challenge to researchers. However, it is on record that there are several ways to cope with the problem in the past (Qin and Oduyemi, 2003). On this note, multivariate statistics like PCA is considered effective tools for identifying the sources and understanding how heavy metals are distributed in the atmospheric particulate matter (Shah *et al.*, 2012).

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Owode area is located in a suburban area is also surrounded by agricultural fields, airport, trees, and residential buildings. Samples were collected for a period of twelve (12) months (from July 2018 to June 2019). The rainwater samples were obtained once a month, with a replicate of the Australian model gauge which is made of high-density polyethylene (HDPE) plastic container (5L), connected to an HDPE funnel. The set-up was placed on the sampling stand 1.6 m above the ground in order to prevent lichen-formation during the sampling period (Figure 2). After collecting, the rainwater was filtered, using quartz (47 mm) filter paper (Onwudiegwu *et al.*, 2016; Abulude *et al.*, 2019).

Fig 2: Pictorial diagram of the sampler used for the collection of TAD samples

Summarized in Figures 3a and 3b are the graphical description showed the mean atmospheric deposition rates ($\text{g m}^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}$). The minimum (100.40) and maximum (285.30) deposition rates were recorded in June and February respectively. The mean deposition rate was 177.73 at 95% confidence intervals. The box plot showed that the symmetric shifted more to the left. The months of April, May, June, July, August, September, and October which are the rain periods were observed to present values lower than the rates observed in the months of November, December, January, February, and March which are the dry periods. The differences in the deposition values obtained during sampling periods could be due to the fact that suspended atmospheric deposits are more prominent in the rain period whereas there is minimal scavenging during the dry season period. Also noted is the influence of harmattan on the north-east trade wind with characteristic dust haze intensified dryness and extensive construction of buildings and urban infrastructure development could have contributed to the high levels TAD in Dry season months (Onwudiegwu *et al.*, 2016). The mean TAD in this study was higher than $0.49 \pm$

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Figure 3a: Graphical Summaries of the Results

Figure 3b: Graphical Summaries of the Results

Table 1: Correlation Coefficient of TAD and Heavy Metals

	TAD	Fe	Cr	Ni	Cu	Pb	Zn
TAD	1						
Fe	0.48	1					
Cr	0.21	0.23	1				
Ni	0.43	0.66	0.12	1			
Cu	0.47	0.87	0.12	0.19	1		
Pb	0.05	0.72	0.84	0.10	0.78	1	
Zn	0.10	0.61	0.18	0.18	0.34	0.19	1

0.46 g m⁻² yr⁻¹ those recorded for the North Atlantic and Labrador Sea (Barraqueta *et al.*, 2019), those from the Eastern Mediterranean 3–50 g m⁻² yr⁻¹ reported by Guerzoni *et al.* (1999), and 1 – 62 1 g m³ day⁻¹ recorded by Onwudiegwu *et al.* (2016). The differences in the results could be due to the differences in which each sample was determined of collected, the discrepancy could be as results of the solubility of aerosols in the different regions, and the combinations of more soluble aerosols transported from dust sources in the regions.

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Table 2: Principal Component Analysis of the Results

	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5	PC6	PC7
TAD	-0.514	-0.107	0.016	-0.329	-0.501	0.597	0.095
Fe	0.250	-0.203	-0.832	-0.019	-0.420	-0.164	0.024
Cr	-0.389	0.462	0.056	0.167	-0.427	-0.444	-0.474
Ni	0.133	0.660	-0.008	-0.249	-0.129	-0.119	0.673
Cu	-0.290	0.401	-0.526	-0.162	0.567	0.262	-0.246
Pb	0.413	0.351	0.011	0.553	-0.204	0.577	-0.158
Zn	0.499	0.118	0.164	-0.685	-0.104	0.057	-0.476
Eigenvalue	2.553	2.003	0.960	0.614	0.478	0.322	0.068
Proportion (%)	36.5	28.6	13.7	8.8	6.8	4.6	1.0
Cumulative (%)	36.5	65.1	78.8	87.6	94.4	99.0	100.0

Figures 3a and 3b also showed the mean heavy metals detected by the XRF instrument. The mean values ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}$) were: The highest average fluxes found for the metals were in the order; Fe (66.92), Cr (0.21), Ni (0.07), Cu (0.3), Pb (0.17), and Zn (9.33). From the study, it was observed that the range of elemental composition was as follows: Fe > Zn > Cu > Cr > Pb > Ni. The high Fe (dust marker) values obtained in the study could be due to the ubiquitous nature in the earth crust and the effects of dust which is prominent in the study due to the fact that the roads surrounding the vicinity are unpaved and poorly maintained (Onwudiegwu *et al.*, 2016).

The Pb contents are the most significant because of the effects (toxic and harmful) at very small concentrations (Gregoriadou *et al.*, 2001). It is known to accumulate in body tissue causing a lot of threats to human health. The results of the Pb in the samples at the location from July 2018 to June 2019 were in the range of 147 and 204 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}$, minimum and maximum concentrations respectively (Figure 3a). The results of the lead content in the air samples collected were a little bit high due to the soil dust. There were high elements present in the dust and were also in the highly polluted class. The origin could be attributed to anthropogenic activities (traffic). Heavy-duty vehicles are frequent on the roads surrounding the vicinity of the sampling point. This is a cause for alarm because the mean value obtained is higher than recommended limits 0.15, 0.5, and 0.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ set by USEPA, (2014), EC (2014), and WHO (2000) respectively. The presence of

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lead in samples could result in hypertension, interference with Vitamin D and calcium metabolism, brain development hindrance in the foetus and young children, damage to tissues and organs in humans and many more (Shamsuddin *et al.*, 2018).

In the comparison of the results obtained in this study, Zinc values were higher than the values ($6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}$) obtained by Azimi *et al.*, (2003) but less than the values obtained by Onwudiegwu *et al.* (2016). The month of July 2018 had the highest value of $15230 \mu\text{g m}^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}$, while that of September had the least ($4393 \mu\text{g m}^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}$). This could be attributed to the difference in the dissolution of the metal in rainwater samples. High Zn in drinking water causes imbalance, vomiting, acute renal failures and abdominal pain. Iron contents revealed that the samples contained between $35375 - 87323 \mu\text{g m}^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}$. The result was lower than those reported for TAD in a Nigerian Island. There are many factors resulting in these differences which ranged from high traffic density, residential places, and high industrial density. High values above WHO, EPA, and NSDWQ standard limits in rainwater can cause stain the container, clothing, and other items, it causes unpleasant taste in foods, can cause diabetes, stomach problems, vomiting, nausea, and hemochromatosis, skin rash or acne (Peninsula Water Conditioning, 2019; Nagendrappa *et al.* 2010). However, anaemia has been reported as a result of iron shortage in humans.

Chromium exhibited minimum and maximum Cr concentrations of $179 \mu\text{g m}^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}$ and $248 \mu\text{g m}^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}$, respectively (Figure 3a). The values are below those reported by Onwudiegwu *et al.* (2016). Natural deposits erosion and coatings removal from water pipes could have been the major causatives of Cr presence in groundwater samples. In drinking-water treatment, oxidative disinfection techniques such as chlorination may oxidise Cr(III) to Cr(VI) (Health Canada, 2016). In the air, Cr is present in the form of aerosols.

It can be removed from the atmosphere by wet and dry deposition (Health Canada, 2016). Chromium exists naturally as an element in rocks, soil, plants, animals and volcano emissions. It is found in drinking water in trivalent (chromium 3) and hexavalent (chromium 6) principal forms (Popoola *et al.*, 2019).

Figure 3b showed that the Ni in this study was between 68 (September) and 87 (August). These values were higher than those observed in Malaysia (Elhadi *et al.*, 2018). Commonly, vehicle exhaust and non-exhaust emissions along the road were considered to be probable contributors to the higher levels of heavy metals in PM_{10} (Wahid *et al.*,

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2014). Ba, remarkably, originated from vehicle exhaust (combustion of gasoline and diesel) and brake wear (Khan et al., 2012). There were serious effects like chronic bronchitis, reduced lung function, and cancer of the lung and nasal sinus on people who have breathed dust containing certain nickel compounds. According to Fortoul *et al.* (2015), constant exposure of animal models to nickel resulted in hyperglycemia and insulin resistance.

According to Hu *et al.* (2012), elemental compounds are an important class (by chemical composition) of PM, seasonal variations have an influence on concentrations and constituents in the atmosphere in cities. Heavy metals in PM can be transported over a long distance, this is the reason why it may be difficult to identify the pollution source areas. In the urban atmosphere, heavy metals sources are mainly from industrial activities (mining, smelting, and fossil fuel combustion), traffic emissions (vehicle exhausts and the products of wear from tires, brake linings, and bearings), and natural sources (minerals, forest fires, and oceans). Atmospheric heavy metal concentrations are actually dependent on the natural background concentrations, economic development level and the overall planning features of a city (Li *et al.*, 2013).

The Pearson correlation results are depicted in Table 1. High correlations were obtained in the followings, Ni/Fe ($r^2=0.66$), Cu/Fe ($r^2=0.87$), Pb/Fe ($r^2=0.72$), Pb/Cr ($r^2=0.84$), Pb/Cu ($r^2=0.78$), Zn/Fe ($r^2=0.61$), while low correlation was between Fe/TAD ($r^2=0.48$). This showed that significant correlations existed among TAD, Fe, Cr, Pb, Ni, and Cu. There was no negative correlation recorded in the matrix. The strong correlations recorded in the elements may indicate the same source or chemical similarity, while the weak correlations may imply different source origin or non-chemical similarity (Ridame *et al.*, 1999). There were strong correlations in soil dust, burning of biomass, automobile-related markers.

Table 3 depicted the PCA of the metals in the samples. The PCA showed that there were significant correlations among TAD, Cr, Pb, Ni, and Cu showed that two principal components with an eigenvalue >1 occupied appropriately 78.8% of the total variance. PC1 was dominated by TAD and Zn, explaining 36.5% of the total variance. PC2 was loaded by Ni, accounting for 65.1% of the total variance. PC3 was loaded by Fe and Cu, accounting for 78.8% of the total variance. The values of the PC1 (TAD and Fe) were close to the background values, showing that the deposits were mainly from natural sources. The values of the heavy metals (Pb and Cr) in PC2 were greater than the corresponding values, which showed that human activities (traffic/vehicular movements) were a major

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influence. The sources of Cu were attributed to agricultural activities, including biomass burning.

Conclusion

The heavy metals (Cr, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, and Pb) were in the TAD. The highest mean values ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}$) were found for the metals were in the order of Fe (66.92), Cr (0.21), Ni (0.07), Cu (0.3), Pb (0.17), and Zn (9.33). From the study, it was observed that the range of elemental composition was as follows: Fe > Zn > Cu > Cr > Pb > Ni. A person's correlation analysis and PCA were applied to identify the sources of heavy metal pollution. The results indicated the TAD and Fe were mainly derived from natural sources, while Cr, Zn, and Pb were originated from agricultural and vehicular traffic.

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